
The Challenge of Foreign Election Observations in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: Since 1999, elections have become regular in Nigeria. From 1999 to 2023 the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) had conducted six consecutive elections. During each of these elections foreign observers trooped into the country in order to study and monitor the electioneering process from campaign to elections. This paper examines the challenges of foreign election observations within the context of how such observations improve or undermine the credibility of these elections. The paper thus argued that credible elections are the hallmark of democratic society, and foreign observations, despite it's controversially helps to improve the credibility of Nigeria's elections through identification of areas of strengths and weakness or problems to be address. Often, INEC has been responding to their observations, which accordingly improves the effectiveness and efficiency of the electoral process in the country.

INTRODUCTION

The nature of rigging, irregularities, vote buying, vote trading and violence associated with election and its process in developing countries of Africa gave a propitious atmosphere for foreign observers to be more interested in monitoring the electoral process and conduct of election in Africa and Nigeria in particular. The emergence of multiparty democracy in Africa was received with great expectations by the citizenry. This optimistic, widely held belief that hinged on the convictions that multiparty democracy will translate into good governance, and unfettered civil rights and freedom. Yet the nature and outcome of elections results in Africa and Nigeria in particular have left many wondering.... most disturbing is that countries such as Kenya, Nigeria, Chad and Niger among other countries that have witnessed electoral violence, tend to remains prone to phenomenon of electoral violence in an unprecedented manner (Niclos et al, 2021). The 1999 general elections in Nigeria was characterized by mass rigging, acrimony, and manipulation of electoral process. Since then, in every election there have been accusations, counter accusations and heavy criticisms by the contending political parties over rigging or manipulation of the entire electoral process (Ademola, Shina, 2013). Due to irregularities, lack of confidence in the electoral process and accusations by the contending political parties, elections tribunal has becoming a normal practice after every periodic election. For the election to earn the true ascription of free, fair and credibility it must be conducted in accordance with universally acceptable standard or measures represent will of the

popular will of the people or electorates. Hence in order to achieve credibility in the electoral process International Institute of peace (2021) posited that the electioneering process in Nigeria has witnessed a proliferation of international and regional election observer missions registering their presence in almost all the elections held in the country. Thus, the increasing integration and participation of election observation by foreign organizations, agencies, into the election process in Nigeria is basically linked to the violence, which increasingly becoming one of the defining elements of the succession elections held in the country.

This proliferation and deep involvement are premised on the idea that foreign election assistance or observation may constitute a robust framework that will help to ensure electoral integrity, the sanctity of the rule of law, and violence free political atmosphere during the elections. Meaning that traditionally, participation of foreign election observers is help the electoral body to actuate the administration of free and credible election by the way of assessing the electoral process through making observations that can help improve future election or enhancing democratic consolidation thereby encouragement of such country to comply with neutral and systematic observations and inputs that have been carefully observed and put forward to curtail the occurrence such practices in the future elections. However, understanding the specifics of how foreign observer missions contribute to the sanitization and credibility of the process in Nigeria has remained largely unclear. Therefore, this study explores the challenge of foreign election observation, what factors account for the proliferation of foreign election observers with competing goals, and why this multiplicity of foreign election has not helped to improve elections in Nigeria. Worryingly, the impact of foreign election observers on the activities of local election observation groups has not had significant implications for the credibility of the electoral process in Nigeria. Some scholars, therefore argued that while successive elections in Nigeria have continued to show a need for external international observation, the outcomes of these interventions have remained contentious, unclear, and counterproductive. Also, the proliferation of FEOs with competing goals has only succeeded in complicating the electoral process and weakening the prospects of local election observation groups. This problem poses a grave danger to Nigeria's democratization process (Niclos et al, 2013). Moreover, it has been argued that, some foreign observers represented biased in their reports for the favour the party they sympathized with and sometimes directly interfere in the electoral process thereby by realising their reports before completion of the process. Hence leading to election related violence and instigate the culture of lack of confidence to process to the electorates, without first submitting their reports to established body regulating the electoral process for redress. Arguably, such scenario

undermines the credibility of the process and it cannot address the challenge related with pre and post-election violence

Election Observations: Issues and Guidelines

Election observation literally refers to the systematic, comprehensive, and accurate gathering of information concerning the laws, processes, and institutions related to the conduct of elections and other factors concerning the overall electoral environment; the impartial and professional analysis of such information; and the conclusions drawn about the character of electoral processes based on the highest standards for accuracy of information and impartiality of analysis. International Democracy and Electoral Institute (IDEA) emphasizes that election observation remains a sine qua non to guaranteeing that elections are conducted in the most accessible and fair manner.²⁹ By so doing, it exposes electoral fraud, weaknesses, and the tendency for violence, thus sustaining the credibility of the electoral process. Election observation is defined as a process which involves the gathering of information and making an informed judgment on the gathered data or information (Guidelines for African Union Electoral Observation and Monitoring Missions, 2002; Nigeria Civil Society Situation Room Toolkit on Election Observation, 2017). Election observation is the process whereby elections in a particular country or locality are observed against set standards by an independent body of observers with the aim of identifying whether the elections conform to accepted guarantees of democratic participation, identifying flaws and challenges and also making recommendations on how the process can be improved in the future (Independent National Electoral Commission {INEC} guideline on election observation and monitoring, 2014). Elections are observed in order to arrive at an informed opinion about the extent to which the entire electoral process conforms to specific national electoral legal frameworks and international standards. From the ideas captured we can easily convince that election observation is a comprehensive analysis and study of the entire electoral process, ranging from preparedness of electoral body, atmosphere for the conduct of the elections, challenges expected to occur during or after elections, administration of the electoral process and level of the political parties and citizen compliance to the established code and conducts governing election.

ISSUES IN ELECTION OBSERVATION

International election observation expresses the interest of the international community in the achievement of democratic elections as part of democratic development including respect for human rights and the rule of law. It assesses election processes in accordance with international principles for genuine democratic elections and domestic law, while recognizing that it is the people of a

country who ultimately determine the credibility and legitimacy of an election process (Declaration of principles for international election observation and code of conduct for international election observers, 2005). In Nigeria there are numbers of issues in the election observation. The independent national electoral commission (INEC 2023) had identified the following issues to observe:

1. State of preparedness for the general election
2. Ability of all stakeholders to participate freely in the electoral process without fear of intimidation and violence
3. Adherence of all stakeholders to the electoral legal framework and to international, continental and regional protocols and standards governing elections.
4. The conduct and behaviour of the security personnel during the electioneering period, especially on electoral day
5. The role and professionalism of the media
6. Adherence to all processes and procedures as required by the electoral legal framework, including opening and closing time of the vote, presence of polling agents, voting procedure, layout of the polling units to protect the sanctity of the vote, polling and counting procedures including sealing of the ballot boxes, announcement and transmission of results.
7. Access of accredited stakeholders to polling units, collation centres and necessary electoral sites
8. The extent to which the electoral outcome reflects the will of the people and the acceptance of the electoral outcome by majority of stakeholders
9. Availability of a well laid out postelection legal adjudication system and dispute resolution mechanisms (INEC, 2023).

Meanwhile going out of the above mentioned issues may lead to controversy and violates and undermines the electoral process. Hence affect the election credibility. That is why it was captured in international election code of conduct (2012) that "Non-partisan election observation and monitoring by citizen's organizations employs in its best practice, long-term observation and analysis that address all parts of the election cycle as well as the broader political context that affects the character and quality of elections. Where non-partisan citizen election observation and monitoring organizations cannot examine every element of a given election process, they should consider the significance of pre-election and post-election factors and place election day process in the proper context of the election cycle as well as the related political environment. This is required in order not to overemphasize election-day developments and thus potentially mischaracterize the nature of the election process. Therefore, independent national electoral commission (2023) clearly stipulated that election observers shall:

The Challenge of Foreign Election Observations in Nigeria

1. Recognise and be respectful of national sovereignty and the laws of Nigeria.
2. Respect the traditions, culture and customs in your area of deployment
3. Comply with security advisory by the security agencies
4. Be non-partisan and neutral in election observation duty
5. Be comprehensive, transparent and accurate in observation and review of the electoral processes and procedures.

GUIDELINES FOR ELECTION OBSERVATION

In every democratic country there is independent body established by the law in order to regulate the administration and the conduct of election and electoral process. Such body also regulate the actions and activities of election observer mission. Under normal and legal trends, elections observers regardless of their country of origin were to conduct their mission under domestic law of the country they trooped in. and they are obliged to issue their reports to such body, for the body to accommodate their inputs and recommendations for the conduct of future elections. Fredric and Uganda (2021) asserted that the activities which conduce to election monitoring and observation that were stipulated in INEC Guideline of 2014 (reversed in 2018 and 2023) are three-pronged. They are pre-election activities, observation of Election Day activities and post-election activities or events.

Pre-Election Activities

Pre-Election activities are in two parts. First, is the Voter Registration and Continuous Registration. Election observers are expected to focus on the following:

- I. Compliance of election officers with national constitutional requirements and international standards in the registration of individuals.
- II. Whether those who are eligible are given sufficient opportunity to register to vote without discrimination with respect to gender, ethnicity, religion or physical disability.
- III. Compliance with rules and procedures established by the commission.
- IV. Incidences of double or multiple registrations by one individual.
- V. Whether individuals are given the opportunity or have access to verify their names in the register.

The next level of Pre-Election activities is the Party Primaries and Candidates Selection Process.

Issues to observe here are as follows:

- I. Compliance with regulations set by INEC in terms of announcement of dates and other requirements for party conventions and congresses.

- II. Compliance with rules and procedures as enshrined in the constitution of the Political Parties, the Electoral Act 2010(as amended) and other extant provisions of the law.
- III. Transparency in the counting of votes and announcement of results.
- IV. Equal treatment and opportunities for all the candidates at the primaries.
- V. Use of money and incentives that confer advantages on some candidates over others
- VI. Adherence of political parties to internal procedures for addressing grievances arising from party primaries.
- VII. The resolution of the disputes arising from party primaries.

Election Day Activities

The activities that take place on Election Day are subdivided into two. First are activities related to casting of ballot and secondly the counting, collation and declaration of results.

Issues to be observed here include:

- I. Timely arrival of poll officials and lay-out of polling stations.
- II. Commencement of accreditation and polling processes.
- III. Conduct and professionalism of poll officials.
- IV. Conduct and professionalism of security agents.
- V. Availability of election materials.
- VI. Compliance with election guidelines by poll officials.
- VII. Secrecy of ballot.
- VIII. Degree of political competitiveness.
- IX. Degree of inclusiveness (ease of participation by all eligible voters including physically challenged people).

Counting, Collation and Declaration of Results

- I. Transparency of conducting vote count
- II. Access of observers, agents and proxies of parties and candidates to counting and collation centres.
- III. Number of votes in relation to number of registered voters.
- IV. Presence of unauthorized persons at counting and collation centres.
- V. Public announcement of results collated.
- VI. Procedures laid down in the regulations for tabulation and transmission of results.

Post-Election Activities or Events.

- I. Capture of details of formal complaints or petitions filed before Election Tribunals
- II. Whether proceedings are conducted in public, open to all interested parties.

- III. Fair and even treatment by adjudicating authorities or courts to all the parties including complainant, witnesses and interested parties.
- IV. Whether the adjudicating authorities appeared to be impartial.
- V. Whether the judicial decisions and rulings are consistent with rulings in similar cases. (Fredric and Ugonma, 2021).

Typology of Foreign Election Observation

Scholars and even election body have categorised the observers basically into two classifications. These are classification based on observer origin and classification based on the duration of the observation. That is the time period often which observer stayed observing and monitoring the process.

Classification based on of the Origin of Observers

According to Adebisi and Loremikan (2013) as the title suggests this categorization is based on the "origin" of the observers. If the observers are coming within the territory of the country conducting the elections, they are called domestic observers. In other words, the monitoring is done by citizen organizations or coalition of organizations autochthonous to the country holding the election. It also includes the observation of party poll-watchers (http://en.Wikipedia.org/wiki/election_monitoring). Apart from the various party poll watchers in Nigeria, independent domestic poll monitors or observers include Committee for the Defence of Human Rights (CDHR), Justice and Equity Organisation, et cetera. The second slice of this category is the International observers. These are observers that originate from international organizations outside the State holding the election or an organization in which it is a member. Examples are European Union (EU), African Union (AU) and Economic Community of West African State (ECOWAS) election observers or monitors.

Classification based on the Duration of Observation

Along here, two types of monitoring have been distinguished. They are Long Term Observers (LTO) and Short Term Observers (STO). According to wikipedia (http://en.Wikipedia.org/wiki/election_monitoring) most observation missions send a small number of long-term monitors (known as LTOS) for period of six or eight weeks. A larger number of short-term observers (known as STOs) then join the mission for the final week of campaign. STOS provide mostly qualitative observation of polling stations and count procedures, with LTOs supplying qualitative analysis and contextual information about the wider political situation (http://en.Wikipedia.org/wiki/election_monitoring). Moreover, some scholars were on the view that, observation classification may also be classify based on the scope of observers. That is to say, whether the observers monitored only

presidential elections or they monitored both presidential, gubernatorial, senatorial and members of state and federal house of assemblies (Ademola and Shina, 2013).

Foreign Election Observation in Nigeria

Literature reveals that election observation is old practice in the democracies. It has been stated that history of election observation can be traced back 1948 when the United Nations led Mission deployed observation missions to South Korea in May 1948. Since then, election observation missions have gained ascendancy in developing countries, especially in Africa, following the democratization wave in the early 1990s (Guy C, 2017). In essence the mission is an activity that seeks, among other things, to critically appraise a country's electoral process to legitimize or condemn it as deemed necessary.¹⁹ As a process, election observation includes activities carried out by both local and international bodies before, during, and after elections, with the aim to pass judgment on the quality of a country's electoral process (Qudri, 1997). Election irregularities, rigging, pre and post elections violence that surrounded the conduct of election and its process in Africa and Nigeria in particular offered conducive environment for foreign election observers FOEs to troop into Nigeria. Ideally to study the process, make certain comments and recommendation that will improve the electoral process and achieve international standard of credibility in the future. In Shina and Demola (2019) it has been cited that "Instructively, there are some established rules, treaties, and conventions that guide electoral activities. They include the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) of 1948; the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination of 1965; the International Convention on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) of 1966; the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe of 1990; the Declaration of Principles for International Election Observation and Code of Conduct for International Election Observation (IEOCCIEO) of 2005; the Africa Union Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance of 2007; and the Declaration of Global Principles for Non-Partisan Election Observation and Monitoring by Citizen Organizations (DoGP) of 2010".

In Nigeria 1999 general election witnessed popular observations from both IFOs and civil society organizations whose reports led the pathway for future elections in Nigeria. After the conduct of the elections The Association of Asian Election Authorities (AAEA), in collaboration with the International Foundation of Electoral System (IFES), observed that the elections were marred by irregularities and fraud in several states across the country. The AAEA and IFES attributed the irregularities to the lack of institutional preparedness and the absence of civil

political culture and orientation among several Nigerians.⁵⁵ Furthermore, the Carter Center, in conjunction with the NDI, was equally vocal about the outcome of the 1999 general elections. In a joint report submitted to the Independent National Electoral Committee chairman, they noted that the elections represented a significant milestone in the country's political history, although characterized by widespread irregularities, electoral fraud, and violence (NDI, 2003). The reports they made has been considered to be a professional input that will help the election body to improve administration of elections and also increase the level of electorate belief on the side of the electoral process and integrity. Hence, not suprising in 2011 many observers become increasingly interested in participating and monitoring the process. IRI noted that, despite the country's history of violent elections, the 2011 elections marked a significant improvement due to reduced violence and the perceived readiness of electoral officials at various polling stations. However, the IRI observed that the failure to maintain ballot secrecy, underage voting, inappropriate campaigning, and post-election violence—the worst in the country's history—undermined the integrity of the electoral process.⁶⁴ According to the NDI, the 2011 elections were historically significant due to the successes achieved compared to the 2007 elections.⁶⁵ However, the NDI raised some problematic issues, such as the unnecessary postponement of the elections and logistical challenges, which slowed the effective distribution of election materials. Others shortcomings included institutional, procedural errors among electoral officers as well as apparent deliberate electoral fraud, both of which constituted significant threats to the 2011 elections and the democratization efforts in Nigeria. Notwithstanding the nonadherence to the early warnings of the FEOs and the apparent disregard for their subsequent reports, FEOs continually have registered their presence in elections, with the 2011 polls reflective in this regard. The FEOs demonstrated keen interest via their presence before elections. This was due to the fireworks, violence, hate speech, intense campaigning, and even threats in the build-up to the 2015 elections. The FEOs, in partnership with spirited Nigerians, played significant roles on two occasions to ensure that the incumbent, Goodluck Jonathan, and his opponent, Muhammed Buhari, were committed to free and fair elections. Also, pledges to accept the electoral outcome was necessary due to the tension-filled political atmosphere the elections generated (NDI, 2011).

Like the previous successive elections in Nigeria, the 2019 elections witnessed the heavy presence of international election observation groups and their series of reports. For instance, the Africa Union (AU) reported that, despite widespread political intimidation and election violence which led to the death of several persons, the 2019 general elections marked a significant improvement in the country's electoral process as they accommodated more involvement by youth via

the Not Too Young to Run Act, institutional preparedness on the part of INEC, and massive involvement and mobilization of the citizenry by civil society organizations. The AU, however, regretted the inability of the country to pass into law proposed electoral reforms, while advising that the INEC must ensure that future elections were well planned to avoid the shifting of polls at the last minute. Also, the European Union Election Observation Mission noted that, apart from the little improvement of the 2019 general elections, the process remained fraught with a series of challenges. The inability of the Internally Displaced Persons to participate, the shift in the date of the elections, the inability of small political parties to access government-owned media, lateness in the distribution of election materials despite the postponement, and pockets of violence were factors that continued to militate against free and fair elections. Thus, the mission called for more transparency, improved communications between the electoral body and other stakeholders, improved engagement of the media and civil society, and more vigilance on the part of the citizenry (Queen, 2019). In addition, the IRI and the NDI observed that, when compared to previous elections, the 2019 general elections fell below expectations, despite their postponement. According to them, the shift in the date of the polls eroded public confidence in the INEC (IRI, 2019). So in 2023 there are a lot changes and INEC has responded and implemented most of the recommendation made by both FEOs and local election observers. In a welcome address delivered by INEC chairman to foreign observers. He assured them that the commission owes a lot to them and their monitoring is yielding and strengthen Nigerian democracy and electoral process. Also, in an effort to prove the ready of preparedness unlike in 2015 and 2019 in 2023 the Presidential election was conducted as slated without postponement which is becoming periodic tradition during elections.

The Challenge and Vitality of Foreign Election Observation in Nigeria

It has been observed that, if FEOs were to act according to well established procedures and comply with guidelines of election observation stipulated in INEC election observation guidelines, there is no doubt they will contribute in achieving free and credible elections. According to Azeez (2013) 'a curious understanding of the activities of FEOS concerning election in Nigeria points to evitable conflicts between their perceived mandates and the expectations of the host country'. There is also growing concern that election monitors are now susceptible to bribery and corruption. This development has influenced some of them to come up with bias or subjective findings and conclusions (field report, 2011). According to Susan et al (2020) "carefully observation of elections held since 1999 suggests that election observation is becoming exciting enterprises for western countries via electoral aid. More problematic is the fact that many of these countries that sponsor election

The Challenge of Foreign Election Observations in Nigeria

observation organizations also embarked on separate observation missions through their embassies". Proliferation of IEOs in Nigeria raised more questions than answers (Giovanni c and Andrea, 2016). The recent experience of the electoral verdicts or reports do not seem to reflect an accurate picture when adequately analysed (Judith k, 2016). Their inability to adequately cover the entire gamut of the national constituency has cast doubt in the validity of their findings, in some cases, election monitoring by foreigners is largely done in cities, while the remote villages where rigging and foul play can be perpetrated are largely left unwatched. Hence, election observers usually confronted with challenge of lost statements, figures, descriptions of events and other evidence that expected to serve as inputs for making informed reports and policy statements that could help improve subsequent election in the country (Oluwabukola, 2011). Their findings sometimes were inaccurate due lack of adequate knowledge of Nigerian political process most of the foreign election observers trooped in few days to election. Hence they will not have much knowledge on pre-election activities such as party primaries, selection of candidates and electoral campaigns (Gropping, 2017).

Factors such as inadequate logistics, paucity of funds and confusion that usually surround conduct of party primaries among other things led to controversies and contradictions to their findings and conclusions (Ugomma and Fredrick, 2021). In the order hand, foreign elections observers have yielded more in Nigeria's electoral process. The FEOs, in partnership with spirited Nigerians, played significant roles on two occasions to ensure that the incumbent, Goodluck Jonathan, and his opponent, Muhammed Buhari, were committed to free and fair elections. Also, pledges to accept the electoral outcome was necessary due to the tension-filled political atmosphere the elections generated. Moreover, despite the challenge foreign election elections observation missions play pivotal role in the sanitization of Nigerian electoral process and achieving credible election based on global mission (Queen E, 2019). While identifying the problems for future improvement of the process, the Institute for Sustainable Democracy in Africa (EISA) Electoral Observer Mission noted that the high level of thuggery, arson, and violence that was recorded during the pre-election period pointed to the fact that the security agencies were not well-equipped to secure the election process. Regarding the elections themselves, the mission pointed out that the lack of a security presence across the country, insecurity, and threats from violent groups ensured that the elections were not held in some local areas. According to the mission, these issues were caused by nonpassage of the Electoral Act Amendment Bill; noninstitutionalization of political parties despite their increasing number; the monetization of elections; and the lack of preparedness on the part of the INEC and the security agencies (Susan et al, 2021). the Africa Union observation

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CONCLUSION

This paper critically studies the challenge of foreign election observation in Nigeria and the role of their observation and the challenge its vitality and how relevance their observation is in transformation and improvement of Nigerian election to meet international standard of credibility. They has examines the competitive nature of foreign elections observers and their contradictory as well as controversial findings and conclusions. The study observed that sometimes bias, sympathy of candidate and lack of manpower and adequate knowledge of the foreign elections observers about the political atmosphere of Nigeria posed serious doubt concerning the integrity of their reports and findings. More worrisome it has been observed that FEOs sometimes violates the established election monitoring guidelines issued by INEC. Hence, undermining electoral process. Therefore, the paper has the following recommendations:

1. That the activities of foreign election observers shall in strictly in accordance with professionalism, ethics and morale conduct.
2. That foreign elections observers shall observe, monitor the electoral process without being partisan in the conduct of their duties.
3. That foreign election observers shall employ more assistants deploy their members to every political ward, so that they may have comprehensive data on the entire election process. Hence their finding will be comprehensive and holistic.
4. That Foreign election observers are to collaborate with civil society organization, and respect Nigerian sovereignty.
5. That foreign election observers are to advise INEC, submits their reports to it before releasing them for public consumption. Sometimes releasing their reports to public consumption without addressing to INEC can be regarded as attack to INEC and Nigeria as a sovereign nation.

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